

Musical Competence of Future Music Teachers and Factors Influencing its Development

Beknazarov Khurshid Kakhramonovich

Independent researcher at TSPU

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Abstract: This article talks about music, the influence of music on a person, musical competence, the interpretation of the concept of musical competence by different scientists, the factors of the development of musical competence of future music teachers.

Keywords: education, upbringing, music, musical instruments, competence, art, pedagogue.

Education and learning cannot be separated from each other. Today, the “mentor-student” tradition, as well as training and education, are carried out in educational institutions. This responsible task, of course, lies with teachers. Efforts in recent years to improve the status of teachers place greater responsibility on them. In fact, it is important for teachers to be cultural, spiritually healthy, have a broad view of the world, deeply know our national values, and have high knowledge in their specialty. This requires teachers to have high knowledge, skills and experience. Teachers with teaching prowess who possess these qualities not only improve the effectiveness of education, but also increase the respect for teachers.

Today is the age of information technology. Times are rapidly evolving. If professors and teachers do not maintain their position as experts by working on themselves, learning and researching according to the times, they lose their place as strong educators in this life. At the moment, scientific and creative innovations and new technologies are being introduced in our republic in order to develop education and bring it to the level of world-class educational institutions. For the purpose of purposeful and high-quality organization of the educational process, state educational standards and qualification requirements are improved, curricula and scientific programs are developed and put into practice. Attention to education, culture and art has increased at the state level, as evidenced by a number of decisions and orders adopted on the development of the industry.

Music expresses the subtle feelings of a person that cannot be expressed in words. Pleasant music helps suppress negative emotions and relieve fatigue. Therefore, listening to music, you can relax, overcome fatigue and mental tension (stress) in people. The great playwright William Shakespeare said: “Music turns anger and hatred into good. He is able to turn kindness into anger and hatred [1]. Music is an art form that creates an artistic image using various sounds and has ideological and emotional content [2]. Music consists of two types: vocal-singing and instrumental. Karl Bucher, a German scientist who lived at the end of the last century, created a theory according to which music arises in the process of labor [3].

The emergence of music is connected with the emergence of art. In other words, the source of music is definitely labor, human labor [4], but it is not said that this music arises only from the rhythms and noises of labor". According to Z.M. Mirkhaidarova, only certain rhythms in Bucher's music arose from the rhythmicity of the labor process.

From the above it can be understood that all hypotheses of the origin of music go back to the human factor and serve man. Music should teach each of us to freely express our feelings through musical sounds. Music should help a person speak, work, listen freely, increase his enthusiasm, lose the feeling of shyness, strengthen the creative abilities of children, fight for life, strengthen their will, increase self-confidence.

We can achieve the development of musical competence in future music teachers if we achieve the dynamics of the formation of musical culture into specific activities.

1. The concepts of "competence" and "competency" are defined differently in the literature and research on pedagogy. Competence (Latin *competo* - I achieve, I deserve, I am worthy) means knowledge, experience [5] in a particular field, the dictionary meaning in Uzbek is "a person who knows well", "a person who has experience" [6]. The concept of "competence" is a concept that initially entered the field of education as a result of psychological and pedagogical research, and today is used as a modern term. Especially recently, when analyzing educational problems, terms such as "competence", "competency", "basic competencies" are widely used. [7]

Analyzing the concepts of competence and competency in the research of B. Khodjaev, based on the opinion of N. A. Muslimov, competence is a set of interrelated personal qualities necessary for productive (effective) and creative activity, and competence is a person's ability to solve any problem in a certain area is interpreted as the acquisition of the necessary competencies.

Before dwelling on the issue of musical competence, let us consider the factors of its occurrence. N.A. Muslimov identified the importance of forming basic, general and special levels of competence in the formation of professional competencies of future vocational education teachers.

From the above we can conclude that, in my opinion, it is appropriate to consider musical competence as a special competence, distinct from abilities and professional competencies.

Research into musical competence has shown that experts and researchers define it differently. For example, one of the CIS scientists N.V. Vasilyeva (Russia) in her study argues that the core of a secondary school music teacher's competence is his musical performance competence, and V.S. Korina (Russia) in her scientific research indicates that the formation of professional thinking is important for the development of musical competence of a music teacher through playing an instrument. A. Aliev (Tajikistan) believes that "musical competence" should be taken into account as an integral part of individual competence in modern society as a priority task in organizing music education in educational institutions. According to one of the European scientists Martin Krause (Germany), musical competence is the concept of a child's individual ability to emotionally and intellectually feel music, sing it (repeatedly) with his own voice or instrument, compose and improvise. M.V. Viktorova (Ukraine) in her study established that musical competence is a complex, multifunctional and individual psychological process based on the integration of professional theoretical knowledge, value orientations and practical skills, as well as personal qualities, which expands the professional capabilities of a person and a future music teacher, influences the student's spiritual world and music - emphasizes that it manifests itself as a high-quality construction of the pedagogical process and the ability to interact with all participants in the educational process.

Uzbek researcher Sh.N. Omankulova interprets musical competence as a component of

professional competence and defines it as follows. "Musical competence means the knowledge, skills and abilities of the future music teacher related to his profession, the ability to organize and manage all pedagogical processes related to musical literacy and musical performance".

Musical competence expands the professional capabilities of the future music teacher and influences the spiritual world of students. Future music teachers will gradually develop their musical competence as a mature specialist as a result of theoretical knowledge of music theoretical sciences, singing and playing skills, music pedagogy, interest in the classical musical art of our national values, and independent work on themselves. It can be seen that musical competence cannot be developed through musical knowledge alone. To develop it, it is necessary to combine theoretical knowledge, performance skills, practical skills and personal qualities. Therefore, the development of musical competence can be interpreted as a complex process.

An individual approach to the development of musical competence is one of the most correct decisions. Since each group of students studying in higher education has a different level of talent, the most effective way is to take an individual approach to their development. Theoretical knowledge of music, the ability to sing and play an instrument are important factors in the development of musical competence in a future music teacher. To master these things, a person must have a wide range of attention, intuition, perception, memory, thinking, imagination and imagination.

In developing musical competence in future music teachers, it is necessary to begin with training and increasing interest in our rich cultural heritage, traditions, folk music, folklore samples and "Shashmakom". It is advisable to introduce them first in the family, in preschool educational institutions, secondary schools, higher and secondary specialized educational institutions. Because every young generation receiving education and upbringing is brought up in the spirit of patriotism, respect for the ancient past and the heritage of their ancestors. The samples of music they listen to over the years gradually shape their musical competence.

If we look at our recent history, we will see and hear that in every family there are people who own musical instruments, and we will see and hear that our national instruments, such as the dutar, doira and rubab, hang in the corner of the living room. This shows that in the life of our people, musical education was first formed in a family environment; love and affection for art is our heritage from time immemorial.

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